

Questionnaire

1 Before Experiment

User Number

Please ask the experimenter for your number.

In wich Room did you play?

Please ask the experimenter if you are not sure.

Room1

Room2

Age

Please write your current age in the box

Gender

Male

Female

Other

Did you know the other player before the experiment?

Yes

No

Are you familliar with VR-devices?

Not at all

Slightly

Moderatly

Very

Extremely

2 Simulator Sickness

Rate the following symptoms by selecting how strongly it affected you while playing the game

General discomfort

- None
-
- Slightly
-
- Moderate
-
- Severe

Fatigue

Feeling of exhaustion or weariness

- None
-
- Slightly
-
- Moderate
-
- Severe

Headache

- None
-
- Slightly
-
- Moderate
-
- Severe

Eyestrain

Did your eyes get tired?

- None
-
- Slightly
-
- Moderate
-
- Severe

Difficulty focusing

- None
-
- Slightly
-
- Moderate
-
- Severe

Increased salivation

Did your body produce excess saliva in your mouth

- None
-
- Slightly
-
- Moderate
-
- Severe

Sweating

- None
-
- Slightly
-
- Moderate
-
- Severe

Nausea

Feeling in stomach that makes you feel like you're going to vomit

- None
-
- Slightly
-
- Moderate
-
- Severe

Difficulty concentrating

- None
-
- Slightly
-
- Moderate
-
- Severe

Fullnes of head

Feeling of a heavy head

- None
-
- Slightly
-
- Moderate
-
- Severe

Blurred vision

- None
-
- Slightly
-
- Moderate
-
- Severe

Dizzy (eyes open)

Feeling of spinning and loosing balance

- None
-
- Slightly
-
- Moderate
-
- Severe

Dizzy (eyes closed)

Feeling of spinning and loosing balance

- None
-
- Slightly
-
- Moderate
-
- Severe

Vertigo

Feeling that the enviroment around you is moving or spinning

- None
-
- Slightly
-
- Moderate
-
- Severe

Stomach awareness

- None
-
- Slightly
-
- Moderate
-
- Severe

Burping

- None
-
- Slightly
-
- Moderate
-
- Severe
-

3 After Experiment

I empathized with the other player

- not at all
-
- slightly
-
- moderately
-
- fairly
-
- extremely
-

My actions depended on the other player's actions

- not at all
-
- slightly
-
- moderately
-
- fairly
-
- extremely
-

The other player's action was dependent on my actions

- not at all
-
- slightly
-
- moderately
-
- fairly
-
- extremely
-

I felt connected to the other player

- not at all
-
- slightly
-
- moderately
-
- fairly
-
- extremely

The other player paid close attention to me

- not at all
-
- slightly
-
- moderately
-
- fairly
-
- extremely

I paid close attention to the other player

- not at all
-
- slightly
-
- moderately
-
- fairly
-
- extremely

I felt jealous about the other player

- not at all
-
- slightly
-
- moderately
-
- fairly
-
- extremely

I found it enjoyable to be with the other player

- not at all
-
- slightly
-
- moderately
-
- fairly
-
- extremely

When I was happy, the other player was happy

- not at all
-
- slightly
-
- moderately
-
- fairly
-
- extremely

When the other player was happy, I was happy

- not at all
-
- slightly
-
- moderately
-
- fairly
-
- extremely

I influenced the mood of the other player

- not at all
-
- slightly
-
- moderately
-
- fairly
-
- extremely

I was influenced by the other player's moods

- not at all
-
- slightly
-
- moderately
-
- fairly
-
- extremely

I admired the other player

- not at all
-
- slightly
-
- moderately
-
- fairly
-
- extremely

What the other player did affected what I did

- not at all
-
- slightly
-
- moderately
-
- fairly
-
- extremely

What I did affected what the other player did

- not at all
-
- slightly
-
- moderately
-
- fairly
-
- extremely

I felt revengeful

- not at all
-
- slightly
-
- moderately
-
- fairly
-
- extremely

I felt schadenfreude (malicious delight)

- not at all
-
- slightly
-
- moderately
-
- fairly
-
- extremely

4 Custom Exploratory Questions

My mood was influenced by the room

- not at all
-
- slightly
-
- moderately
-
- fairly
-
- extremely

The room made me feel...

- very comfortable
-
- comfortable
-
- neutral
-
- uncomfortable
-
- very uncomfortable

My mood was influenced by the coloring of the room

- not at all
-
- slightly
-
- moderately
-
- fairly
-
- extremely

The coloring made me feel...

- very comfortable
-
- comfortable
-
- neutral
-
- uncomfortable
-
- very uncomfortable

I would change the coloring of the room into

If you wouldn't change the color, leave the question blank

My mood was influenced by the size of the room

- not at all
-
- slightly
-
- moderately
-
- fairly
-
- extremely

The size made me feel...

- very comfortable
-
- comfortable
-
- neutral
-
- uncomfortable
-
- very uncomfortable

I would make the room...

In depth and width

- Bigger
-
- Smaller
-
- I would't change the room

My mood was influenced by the furnishing of the room

- not at all
-
- slightly
-
- moderately
-
- fairly
-
- extremely

The furnishing made me feel...

Everything that couldn't be moved

- very comfortable
-
- comfortable
-
- neutral
-
- uncomfortable
-
- very uncomfortable

I would add _____ as furnishing

If you wouldn't add furnishing, leave the question blank

My mood was influenced by the interactive objects

Interactivee objects = objects, that the player can interact with. For example picking it up and trowing it

- not at all
-
- slightly
-
- moderately
-
- fairly
-
- extremely

The interactive objects made me feel...

Interactivee objects = objects, that the player can interact with. For example picking it up and trowing it

- very comfortable
-
- comfortable
-
- neutral
-
- uncomfortable
-
- very uncomfortable

I would add _____ as a interactive object

If you wouldn't add extra interactibe objects, leave the question blank

5 Endseite
